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FEATURES OF ADAPTATION TO COMPLETE REMOVABLE LAMELLAR DENTURES

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Abstract

The aim of the study was to study the complaints of patients during the period of adaptation to complete removable lamellar dentures after 30 days of using the dentures. A survey was conducted of 254 patients who were made complete dentures for the quality of the latter, in a day, 1-5 days and 5-30 days after the delivery of prostheses. During the examination period, the most frequent complaints of patients were lack of functionality, difficulty in speech and chewing, and irritation of the mucous membranes. These complaints were found in patients of the second and third age groups. Complaints about the lack of aesthetic appearance were most common in the first age group.

Key words: secondary adentia, complete removable laminar prosthesis, orthopedic treatment.

The main orthopedic treatment of patients with complete secondary adentia is the manufacture of complete removable lamellar prostheses (RPPP). According to the literature, the absence of any complaints after the delivery of PSCP to a patient is a rare condition [2]. It is known that a prosthesis, no matter how good and beautiful it may be, causes considerable discomfort to a person. The main condition for assessing the improvement in the patient's well-being and appearance is adaptation to this initial change [1]. Patients are always suspicious of orthopedic treatment. Therefore, some patients subconsciously hesitate to use prostheses [3]. With a positive result of prosthetics, the period of adaptation of the patient to prostheses is significantly shortened, which mainly depends on the literacy of the doctor and dental technician [5]. The vast majority of

patients are satisfied with their dentures, but not all. However, it is impossible to satisfy a certain group of patients. The dissatisfaction of such patients consists of a series of chains with periodic and non-permanent complaints, as well as prosthetics and accompanied by repeated correction of the prosthesis, which consists in grinding off the traumatic mucous membrane areas of the prosthesis [6]. Before handing over the prosthesis to the patient, the orthopedist must clarify the factors that violate fixation and stabilization, as well as the length and sharpness of the edges, the formation of roughness and bulges on the inner surface of the prosthesis. To significantly facilitate adaptation to prostheses, it is necessary that the patient visit an orthopedist after 24 or 48 hours to correct prostheses. Even slight discomfort on the mucous membrane of the prosthetic

bed must be eliminated so as not to lead to traumatic damage. In general, the first few visits to the doctor are carried out at very short intervals, while long-term follow-up of the patient has a significant advantage [4]. Each orthopedic dentist, after the delivery of prostheses to the patient, can make a whole list of complaints made by patients [2].

The aim of the study was to study the complaints of patients until full adaptation to complete removable lamellar dentures.

Materials and methods

In 2014-2017, in the dental clinic of the Azerbaijan Medical University, we made complete removable lamellar dentures for 254 patients (120 men, 134 women) aged 45-85 years. We divided all patients into groups by age and gender to study the most common complaints during the period of adaptation. The distribution of patients by age and sex is presented in Table 1. The greatest need for prosthetics was aged 60-74 years (48.82%).

Table 1

gender \ age	45-59	60-74	75-89	90<
Man	45	54	20	1
woman	52	70	10	2
total	97	124	30	3

Results and its discussion

We have made 508 complete removable plate dentures for both jaws. Table 1 also shows that the number of complete removable lamellar dentures was in the group 45-59 years old (44.0%), in the group 60-74 years old (49.0%), 75-90 years old (13.0%). The level of need for prosthetics of the main clinical contingent was taken into account when planning orthopedic dental care. Need of 120 (54 men, 66 women) patients in

orthopedic treatment with the use of complete removable dentures was revealed. 134 people (66 men, 68 women) needed primary prosthetics. In addition, only 42 out of 120 people (35.0%) who needed to be replaced did not use complete removable lamellar dentures, 30 people (25.0%) used a prosthesis even though it was of poor quality, 48 people (40, 0%) used prostheses without complaints.

Picture 1. Complaints of patients about the size, difficulty chewing and speech
Blue is the size of the prosthesis, brown is speech, green is chewing.

On the day the prosthesis was delivered, 96% of patients complained about the size of the prosthesis, after a day the complaints decreased by 52%, on the 5th day of complaints there were 32%, after a month of using prostheses, complaints amounted to only 8% (Fig. 1) It is quite natural that after the delivery of the prosthesis, the patient perceives it as a large foreign body in his mouth, then the mode of getting used to the prosthesis is switched on, and this complaint practically disappears.

On the day the prostheses were delivered, complaints of poor fixation were noted in 37% of patients in the upper jaw, in the lower jaw 62% after 1 day, in the upper jaw 18%, in the lower jaw 36%, after 5 days in the upper jaw 8% and 21% lower jaw, and after 5-30 days 2% in the upper jaw and 11% in the lower jaw (Fig. 2).

Picture 2.

During the adaptation period, complaints about fixation, irritation of the mucosa and aesthetics of prostheses. 1 fixation on h/h, 2 fixation on h/h, 3 mucosal irritation h/h, 4 mucous irritation h/h, 5 Aesthetics v/h, 6 Aesthetics l/h

Practice shows that patients need some time to fully adapt to complete removable dentures.

On the day of complete removable dentures, speech problems were observed in 58% of patients, in 48% after 1 day, in 38% after 1-5 days and in 12% after 5-30 days (Fig. 1).

On the day of the delivery of complete removable dentures, problems with the act of chewing were observed in 88% of patients, a day later in 78%, after 1-5 days in 72% and after 5-30 days in 42% (Fig. 1). The mechanism of chewing food consists of a set of interrelated processes. Teeth are only a significant part of this process. This process includes the tongue, lips, cheeks and salivary glands.

During the delivery of complete removable dentures in the upper jaw, irritation of the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed was noted in 37% of patients and 63% in the lower jaw, after a day the complaints became 32% v/h and 58% n/h, after 5 days 18% v/h and 21% n/h, after 5-30 days 6% v/h and 9% n/h. (Fig.2) In general, it is important that dentures do not cause traumatic damage, i. did not irritate the oral mucosa. In some cases, a patient with traumatic injury or discomfort may not be able to eat, swallow, or even speak. The orthopedic dentist needs to eliminate all these complaints so that the patient can comfortably use the manufactured prostheses. Our study showed that it takes from 1 to 30 days to return to a full-fledged functional

state. All this is purely individual, someone needs 1 day, someone much more.

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